

Contents of Report

Created by <https://lipidomicstandards.org>, version v2.4.0

Separation Workflow	1
Overall study design	1
Lipid extraction	1
Analytical platform	1
Quality control	2
Method qualification and validation	2
Reporting	2
Sample Descriptions	2
PLOP4 / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)	2
Lipid Class Descriptions	3
1) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification	3
1) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification	3
2) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification	4
2) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification	4
3) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid identification	5
3) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification	5

Separation Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study	Trapped ion mobility spectrometry guided molecular discrimination between plasmalogens and other ether lipids in lipidomics experiments		
Document creation date	10/21/2024	Corresponding Email	Jakob.Koch@i-med.ac.at
Principal investigator	Jakob Koch	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Institute of Human Genetics, Medical University of Innsbruck	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	2-phase system	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	None	Special conditions	Sonication, Mixer mill 2 min 20 Hz
2-phase system	Folch	Derivatization	none

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate, Formic acid	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	50000
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	20
Separation type 1	LC	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Profile mode
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.15
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
MS type	TOF	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	40000
MS vendor	Bruker	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	25
Ion source	ESI	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Centroid mode
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	Yes
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank	Type of QC sample	Reference material

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
-------------------	----

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	10.5281/zenodo.11143478	Raw data upload	Yes
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	For full code to reproduce analysis see Supplementary Dataset deposited at ZENODO

Sample Descriptions

PLOP4 / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Storage temperature	-80 °C
Storage and collection conditions	Available	Additives	None
Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze (min)	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	N2	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Time to freeze (min)	0.5	Sample homogenization	Yes
Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes	Sample homogenization solvent	1xPBS

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) PE[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	IMS
Fragments for identification		CCS verified by standard	Yes
Fragment name			
FA1(+O)			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	Benchmarking
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	Yes
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check on:	Isomeric overlap		

1) PE[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	was not the aim of the study.

2) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Check on:	Isomeric overlap
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Limit of detection	No
Identification level	Species level	RT verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Additional dimension/techniques	IMS
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	CCS verified by standard	No
Isotope correction at MS2	No	How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	Benchmarking, not able to fully separate in our study.
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Background check at MS1	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Which assumptions were presumed?	portion of samples only contained 1-O-alkyl species (PEDS1 deficient)	Further identification remarks	done to the best of my knowledge

2) PE O[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	not applicable to study.

3) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Check on:	-
MS Level for identification	MS1, MS2	Limit of detection	No
Identification level	Species level	RT verified by standard	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Fragments for identification		Additional dimension/techniques	IMS
Fragment name			
FA2(+O)			
-FA2(+HO)			
Isotope correction at MS1	No	CCS verified by standard	Yes
Isotope correction at MS2	No	How was/were the additional dimension(s) used?	Benchmarking
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Was a model used to predict lipid molecule separation?	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Background check at MS1	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	No
Which assumptions were presumed?	subset of samples only contains 1-O-alkenyl PEs.	Further identification remarks	Was done to the best of my knowledge

3) PE P[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	was not the aim of the study